

INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA AUTENTIK MATERIALLARDAN
FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o'quvchilarda ingliz tili o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishni shakllantirishda autentik materiallarning ahamiyati haqida muallifning fikr va mulohazalari bayon qilingan. Shuningdek, autentik materiallarning turlari va vazifalari xususida ma'lumot berilgan. Ushbu materiallardan ingliz tili darslarida foydalanish uchun namunalar ham ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Xalqaro tillar, ingliz tili, autentik material, tinglash-ko'rish materiallari, visual materiallar, turkumlar, haqiqiy, madaniyat, yangiliklar, filmlar

Abstract. This article describes the author's thoughts and opinions about the importance of authentic materials in the formation of students' interest in learning English. Also, information is given about the types and functions of authentic materials. Samples for using these materials in English lessons are also shown.

Keywords: International languages, English, authentic material, audio-visual materials, visual materials, series, real, culture, news, movies

Аннотация: В данной статье изложены мысли и мнения автора о важности аутентичных материалов в формировании интереса учащихся к изучению английского языка. Также дана информация о видах и функциях аутентичных материалов. Также показаны образцы использования этих материалов на уроках английского языка.

Ключевые слова: Международные языки, английский, аутентичный материал, аудиовизуальные материалы, визуальные материалы, сериалы, реальность, культура, новости, фильмы

Ma'lumki, bugungi globallashtirilgan zamonda chet tilini o'rganish hamda uni kundalik hayotda qo'llay bilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ayniqsa, yoshlarda xalqaro tillarni o'rganishga bo'lgan talab va ehtiyoj yanada oshib bormoqda. Ishonchli manbalardan biri bo'lgan Acolad saytining xabar berishicha chet tillari orasida ingliz tili eng ko'p o'rganilayotgan tillar qatorida birinchi o'rinda turar ekan. Buning sababi sifatida ingliz tili ta'lim, biznes, xalqaro diplomatik aloqalar tili ekanligi ta'kidlangan.

Shunday vaziyatda ingliz tilini samarali o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan usullarni ishlab chiqish dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Dars jarayonida o'rganilgan ingliz tilini haqiqiy ingliz jamiyatida qo'llashda bir qancha tafovutlar yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Bunda autentik materiallardan muntazam foydalanish ushbu masalaning yechimi bo'la oladi. Autentik inglizcha “authentic” so'zidan olingan bo'lib, “haqiqiy, asl” degan ma'noni anglatadi.

Autentik materiallar yoki matnlar atamasi odatda til o'rgatish uchun mo'ljallanmagan har qanday “yozma yoki og'zaki matnlarga” nisbatan qo'llaniladi. Gazeta maqolasi, rok qo'shig'i, roman, radio intervyu, o'yin o'ynash bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar va an'anaviy ertaklar haqiqiy matnga misoldir. Dialog va romanning lingvistik jihatdan soddalashtirilgan versiyasi haqiqiy matn hisoblanmaydi. [1, 10]

Olim Gebxard asl materiallarni uch turkumga ajratib, har biriga alohida to'xtalib o'tadi.

1. Autentik tinglash-ko'rish materiallari.

U televideniya reklamalari, viktorina shoulari, multfilmlar, yangiliklar, komediya shoulari, filmlar, seriallar, roman va hikoyalarning professional audioyozuvlari, radio reklamalari, qo‘shiqlar, hujjatli filmlardan iborat. Ushbu turkum o‘zining til o‘rganish va o‘rgatish bo‘yicha samaradorligi bilan mashhur hisoblanadi. Birinchidan, ular tinglash va talaffuz qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ikkinchidan, ingliz tili o‘rganuvchilari ingliz madaniyati, urf-odatlarini, munosabatlari, belgilari, san’ati, psixologik va ijtimoiy farqlarini o‘rgana olishadi.

2. Autentik vizual materiallar.

Slaydlar, fotosuratlar, rasmlar, bolalar rasmlari, tayoqchalar rasmlari, so‘zsiz ko‘cha belgilari, siluetlar, jurnal rasmlari, otkritka rasmlari, so‘zsiz rasmlar, markalar va rentgen tasvirlari ushbu toifaga kiritilgan bo‘lib, bu har bir o‘quvchining qiziqishi va tasavvurini rivojlantirish uchun juda foydali.

3. Autentik matn materiallari.

Oxirgi toifa o‘qish qobiliyatini va so‘z boyligini oshirish uchun zarur vositalar bilan to‘la. Ular gazeta maqolalari, kino reklamalari, qo‘shiq matnlari, restoran menyusi, ko‘cha belgilari, ma’lumot broshyuralari, xaritalar, teleko‘rsatuvlar, komikslar, tabriknomalar va avtobus jadvallari.[2, 3]

Quyida til o‘rganuvchilarining aynan o‘qish ko‘nikmasini rivojlantirishga mo‘ljallangan autentik matn materialiga kiruvchi maqoladan foydalangan holda tayyorlangan dars ishlanmasini ko‘rib chiqishimiz mumkin.

Your writing

We invite our readers to give their opinions by writing an article on the following subject:

Bullying

How serious a problem is bullying in schools where you live, and what can be done to stop bullying at school?

The best article will be published in the next issue of our magazine.

The happiest days of your life?

by Jamie Field

School days should be a happy time in a young person's life. **What can make people's lives a misery during this time, then?** In my opinion, there is one word which answers this question – bullying.

Unfortunately, bullying is quite common in schools where I live. It can affect students of any age, and both boys and girls. **A friend of mine** had a very negative experience at school last year as an older boy continually called him names and sometimes used to post nasty messages about him on Facebook. **Obviously,** my friend felt very upset about this and it affected his self-confidence. Some days, he didn't want to come to school at all.

What can people do to stop this problem? **Personally,** I think teachers need to be aware that bullying may be happening in their classes and be very strict when they have a case of bullying. Another thing teachers could do is prepare lessons to talk about the problem with their pupils, which might make bullies realise how badly they hurt their victims. As for students, if they find out a classmate is being bullied, they should support them as much as possible and let a teacher know.

Bullying can be a nightmare but there are things we can do to prevent it. **Hopefully,** one day all students will be able to go to school without fear of being bullied.

Top Tips for writing

1. **Use a catchy title to get people interested.**
2. **Ask direct questions to get the reader's attention.**
3. **Use opinion adverbs to introduce your points.**
4. **Give a real-life example or talk about personal experience.**
5. **Choose a neutral or informal style, depending on the audience.**
6. **Divide your ideas into clear paragraphs.**

Ushbu ishlanma o'quvchiga yangi so'zlarni o'rganish, o'qish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish uchun mashqlar beribgina qolmay, maqola tuzilishini o'rganib chiqib, aynan shu kabi maqola yozish uchun ko'rsatma va ma'lumotlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

Preparation

Do you know how to write a magazine article? Circle True or False for these sentences.

1. An article should always be written using formal language. True False
2. You should use paragraphs when writing an article. True False
3. Don't express your opinion in an article. True False
4. Your article should have a catchy title. True False
5. You should ask the reader questions in your article. True False

1. Check your understanding: multiple choice. Circle the best option to complete these sentences.

1. The writer thinks a person's school life is never really happy / is the happiest time in their life / can be made miserable by bullying.
2. Bullying is common / rare / happening everywhere, in the writer's experience.
3. The writer's friend was bullied at school / online / at school and online.
4. The boy who was being bullied had a very strange / funny / bad experience.
5. The writer thinks students / teachers / parents could do more about this problem.
6. Students / Teachers / Parents can also support people who are being bullied

2. Check your writing: word 2 word – questions. Write the words in the correct order to make questions.

1. is What exactly bullying?
.....
2. do Why like behave bullies this?
.....
3. the bullying? are What consequences of
.....
4. a you tell teacher or Should parent?
.....
5. stop can What do bullying? to people
.....

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